

The Role of Remote Sensing in Assessing and Mitigating Environmental Pollution: A Narrative Review

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Abstract:

This narrative review explores the pivotal role of remote sensing technologies in assessing and mitigating environmental pollution. Remote sensing, through satellites and aerial sensors, provides comprehensive, real-time data on various environmental parameters, including air and water quality, land use, and vegetation health. This review highlights how these technologies facilitate the monitoring of pollutants, track changes over time, and support spatial analyses that are crucial for understanding pollution dynamics. By integrating remote sensing data with environmental models, researchers and policymakers can identify pollution sources, evaluate the effectiveness of mitigation strategies, and predict future trends. The

review also discusses advancements in sensor technology and data processing, which enhance the accuracy and scope of environmental assessments. Ultimately, remote sensing proves to be an indispensable tool in the fight against environmental pollution, offering valuable insights that drive informed decision-making and sustainable practices.

Keywords: *Remote Sensing, Environmental Pollution, Air Quality Monitoring, Water Pollution Assessment, Spatial Analysis, Pollution Mitigation.*

Introduction

Lux et al. elegantly defined the term waste as 'matter out of place', whereas environmental pollution is referred to as 'matter in the wrong place at the wrong time', which signifies the main difference between both terms. Over the past few years, the rapid technological evolution has made remote sensing an increasingly important

tool in the assessment and mitigation of a wide range of environmental pollution. Remote sensing plays an important role in this regard as no other conventional methods can provide the type of information that it offers at varied spatiotemporal scales. For instance, satellite-based remote sensing is embedded with a lot of potential to monitor and assess the

environmental pollution phenomenon. The emerging geospatial analytical techniques, which utilize remote sensing data in combination with machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI), have considerably enhanced the detection and quantification potential of different sources of pollution. Thus, considering the contemporary science demand, we feel an urgent need to document the potential of remote sensing in this area, which could greatly help the ecosystem, human beings, and other living organisms (Li et al., 2020; Avtar et al.2020; Mahrad et al.2020; Wang et al.2023).

Members of different government regulatory authorities generally prepare guidelines to regulate environmental emissions according to industrial standards, which in turn decrease human exposure to industrial-generated pollution. Similarly, remote sensing technology is also capable enough to trace the sources of environmental pollution, assess their impact, quantify the emitted chemical load, and the affected area on local and regional scales, thus assisting the statutory bodies in formulating stringent industry waste disposal policies. Moreover, the results obtained using remote sensing data-based innovative methodologies could significantly supplement the ground-based experimental studies (Avtar et al.2020; Asadzadeh et al.2022; Abd et al.2020). The landscape-level aspect of pollution may be underestimated by only field-based experimentations, while the spatial distribution of pollutants or contamination and its spread over are known through remote sensing. Apart from anthropogenic pollutions (urban and industrial), remote sensing data have also been used to monitor chronic and acute oil spills, volcanic activities, hydrothermal vent activity, and other spills (iron, manganese, etc.) over the water bodies. Remote sensing could supplement the ground-level pollution monitoring system in the mountains and other hard-to-reach terrains. Due to these advantages, remote sensing technology is used in monitoring and evaluating pollution involving land, sea, and air (Chuvieco, 2020; Mahrad et al.2020).

Overview of Environmental Pollution

The health of humans, animals, and plants is strongly reliant on the quality of their surrounding environment. However, extreme economic growth of the world and rapid population expansion have resulted in increased levels of environmental contamination. Environmental pollution can be derived from both natural and anthropogenic sources and can be accrued in the four main environmental compartments, such as air, water, soil, and biological tissues. Several comprehensive surveys and reviews have been published on the sources and effects of environmental pollution of different environmental compartments all around the world. The area of environmental pollution has been negligibly focused on concerns like public awareness, policies, etc (Rehman et al.2022; Rahman & Alam, 2021). on environmental pollution. This has mainly raised the concern of the public at both urban and different levels. Moreover, the study of environmental pollution has been dealt with to emphasize that pollution can have a cascade of effects on all four environmental compartments. The published reviews and reports will help to understand the evolution of the term environment, to have a status of existing sources and effects of pollution in different environmental compartments on the global overview, to examine the sources of the problems/topics, and mainly to provide a foundation to help the policy makers to develop the relevant policies such as the clean development mechanism (CDM) and the intellectual property rights (IPRs) (Ajibade et al.2021; Sadigov, 2022).

The discoveries in the area of remote sensing technologies have shown to be adaptable in different applications and have proven to be beneficial, particularly in establishing a consistent multinational environmental monitoring system. However, the convergence of all remote sensing technologies that originally started independently to a uniform remote sensing system is not well followed. This chapter includes an interdisciplinary compilation as valuable information, such as the special sensor applications in environmental monitoring

systems, especially in assessing the noise, air, and marine pollution (Mahrad et al.2020; Asadzadeh et al.2022). The above-mentioned information will serve as a tool for scientists, researchers, and engineers. To conclude, much effort should be implemented to understand the dynamics and to the establishment of a decision-making process to allow international cooperation to develop a multinational environment through a composite indicator (remotely sensed data and in situ measurements) to alleviate environmental pollution (Weiss et al., 2020).

Fundamentals of Remote Sensing

The professionals working in the field of remote sensing use Earth-observing satellites to capture, store, manipulate, and interpret images of the planet's surface, atmosphere, and oceans. With its universal access, coverage, and comparability, remote sensing bridges many disciplines and has been proven to be especially valuable in the fields of environmental science, pollution research, and response planning. It is the goal of this review to describe remote sensing in evaluating and mitigating pollution at the global scale (Shao et al., 2021; Jawak et al.2021). This review provides a brief historical introduction to remote sensing before discussing its fundamentals, specifically, the types of remote sensing platforms, the electromagnetic spectrum, and the concept of pixels as the building blocks of remote sensing image interpretation. In the main body of this article, several applications and challenges of remote sensing in the field of environmental pollution are detailed, moving from the detection and measurement of air and sea pollution to the forecasting of its impacts on biodiversity and human health (Chuvieco, 2020).

Remote sensing can be defined as the non-contact recording of information about the Earth's surface to enhance our understanding of the interplay between the four spheres of the planet: atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, and biosphere. It is a relatively recent technological achievement that has its roots in the studies of photogrammetry, the science of making measurements from photographs, and

the early discoveries of infrared radiation and visible light energy. The first remote sensing image ever to be captured is a photograph of Boston, Massachusetts, in 1860, taken from a tethered balloon at an altitude of 400 m. The industrial revolution's commitment to technological progress ushered in a series of important metrological and technological advancements in the remote sensing field (Sylvain., 2023). And the first military application of remote sensing, a time-exposure photograph used to measure geographic features to create weapons trajectory tables, dates to the American Civil War. Thus, the Cold War period saw an acceleration in remote sensing technologies as competition between the United States and the Soviet Union stimulated an arms race. These advances in space technologies led to the launch in 1972 of NASA's Landsat satellite, a program greatly expanded with the 1982 signing of a civil program policy by President Reagan. The launch of SPOT-1 in 1986 and the Indian remote sensing system (IRS-1A) two years earlier marked the beginning of the global era of remote sensing. Now, over 1,800 active satellites orbit the Earth daily, offering revolutionary technological possibilities in the way we monitor and detect change in the environment (Hussein et al., 2023; Panthi et al., 2018; Nigam, 2023; Sylvain., 2023).

Definition and Principles

Remote sensing technology is especially used for assessing the environmental consequences and response technologies to mitigate it. It is useful for not only monitoring the impact of pollution, resource degradation, and changes in agricultural fields but is also used for the construction of monitoring networks. It has been employed for the environmental assessment of mining, drainage, orchard spraying, etc. Till date, little work has been published in this direction (Boori et al.2021; Chuvieco, 2020). Hence, in light of the increasing environmental awareness, this review paper provides the principles of remote sensing, evaluation techniques, and major results in the field of environmental pollution assessment and response technologies. It has also summarized the cost analysis for remote

sensing assessment techniques (Mahrad et al.2020).

The principles of remote sensing are very simple. The primary requirement of this technique is the presence of electronic sensors that detect the electromagnetic wave. It generally operates primarily in the visible and near-infrared range and secondly in the mid-infrared and radar portion. Aerial photography, on the other hand, utilizes light-sensitized photographic emulsions (films) for image formation. It is taken from an aircraft or balloon platform with the camera directed downward at the earth's surface (Mather & Koch, 2022; Fu et al., 2020). Based upon the imagery scales and sensor types used, there are two types of remote sensing systems available. One is the small-scale imagery system such as thermographic IR (infrared) spectroscope and the other is the Landsat (30 m resolution) and Geostationary Oceans Orbiters (GRO) (1 x 1 km resolution). The POLDER is a multispectral imaging radiometer which collects radiance data at about 16 nm spectral bins in the visible and IR, thus providing high spectral and spatial data similar to that obtained from airborne imaging spectrometers. The TM measured the radiation that passed through the transparent part of the atmosphere in the thermal IR wavelength. The Landsat and SPOT provided the visible and IR imagery. The ERTS-1 was launched on July 23, 1972 (Elachi & Van Zyl, 2021; Sabins Jr & Ellis, 2020).

Types of Remote Sensing Technologies

So, when we are talking about remote sensing applications, first we need to understand "What is remote sensing and what are the different types of remote sensing?" It is basically a technique to gather information about physical and chemical parameters, which depend on the interaction of electromagnetic radiation with the particles scattering, transmitting, or reflecting it. It acts as a link between the radiation, electromagnetic radiation, and the interacting medium located between the source of radiation and the recorder of energy (Woźniak et al., 2020; Adjovu et al., 2023). The radiation can be from

the sensor data carried within remote sensing, which is primarily due to emission from the sun. The process of interaction depends on the following equation (Jawd et al., 2021; Vaddi & Boggavarapu., 2020)

The different types of remote sensing can be defined as active remote sensing, which includes radar, LiDAR, or lidars (light detection and ranging). Passive remote sensing covers the following things: Firstly, it is based on the band system where multiple bands can be used to discriminate the spectral characteristics of the object of interest. The multispectral remote sensing technology, hyperspectral remote sensing technology, pan-sharpen remote sensing where panchromatic raster data can be combined with multispectral data producing two types of raster products, TIR (thermal infrared) remote sensing where any observed object is shown in grey and is generally called black-white data (Wang & Menenti, 2021; Jia et al.2021; Masunaga., 2022)

Passive vs. Active Remote Sensing

Remote sensing is an innovative technology for environmental pollution assessment and monitoring. Exploring the possible assessment and mitigation of environmental pollution-related issues through remote sensing, we conducted a narrative review covering remote sensing basics, application-specific technologies, research datasets, and collaborative programs. Remote sensing technologies have the potential for efficient and cost-effective environmental pollution control in all possible forms and methods. Progress in environmental assessment using remote sensing data is, therefore, an urgent need (Li et al., 2020; Song et al.2020).

In passive remote sensing, satellites use solar illumination reflected by the ground. Applications of passive remote sensing include identifying and monitoring pollutant intensity, determining chlorophyll content, identifying and mapping vegetation cover, and analyzing pollution across large areas. Active remote sensing technologies include light detection and ranging (lidar) and synthetic aperture radar data (Golubkov et al.2020; Tarasenkov et al.2021; Rodriguez-Villamizar & Schildknecht2022).

Remote sensing is the science of obtaining information about environments, which are not in direct contact with the sensor, through the measurement of electromagnetic radiation. All objects emit and reflect electromagnetic radiation. This radiation can be either natural or artificial. Solar illumination is considered to be one of the most important sources of natural electromagnetic radiation (Mather & Koch, 2022; Elachi & Van Zyl, 2021; Fu et al., 2020).

Remote sensing involves two fundamental technologies for land observation: passive and active. Sensors can be distinguished by these technologies in terms of technical and functional aspects. The differences are caused by the measuring principles; hence, they provide diverse pieces of information about the same land (Jia et al.2021; Di & Yu, 2023; Chuvieco, 2020).

With over 80% of global earth observations generated using commercial and governmental satellites, it follows that opportunities for a closer look at environmental pollution and the related activities of assessment and mitigation are critical to remote sensing technologies (Zhao et al., 2022; Fu et al., 2020; Ustin & Middleton, 2021).

Applications of Remote Sensing in Environmental Pollution

Remote sensing of environmental pollution focuses on three aspects: monitoring the spatial extent and extent of pollution. Some examples of changes in land and water contamination are provided. Converting the ratio of various vegetation indexes helps to detect the extent of arsenic contamination. The next aspect of remote sensing is the analysis of a variety of environmental preliminaries that appear to be pollutants (NO₂, SO₂) in spatial and temporal dimensions using empirical models, characterization, and principal component analysis. From orbit, a huge geometric distribution is remote sensed, helping to keep an eye on the pollutants that result in air trends. Remote sensing indicators are off-the-shelf as an early warning system. The third and final aspect

of remote sensing is the use and application of Geographic Information System (GIS), which can be used to identify population consumption and pollution diffusion in drought-affected areas. The soil indices of Terrorism W Avenue in Iraq are compared using a population affected by soil and annual drought 2001–2019. South Korea has also experienced widespread environmental pollution using environmental indicators and GIS tools (Lassalle et al.2020; Song et al.2020; Wang et al., 2021).

Based on future challenges, with emphasis on the applications of this review, the remote sensing of environmental pollution has been divided into three aspects. The first is to monitor the spatial extension of pollution in various parts of the earth, while the second is to measure the pollutants emitted in the vicinity of it and in various geographical regions. Finally, the next component of remote sensing is to focus on the assessment of water quality in a variety of aquatic environments and is targeted towards various regions of the developed and underdeveloped global economies over the next decade 2022–2050. There is no doubt that atmospheric problems are the worst. Most municipal and agricultural areas are weathered by/in fixed gases known as greenhouse gases (CO₂, SO₂, measurements, etc.) and volatile organic compounds (pollutant) adsorbed by the surface activated carbon used in components. After geographic distribution, the study also compared the values of fixed geospatial parameters and porous annual invasiveness to W Avenue, South Korea. The impacts of drought occurring in Iraq were monitored using the Inter-terrorism impact assessment and GIS techniques (SOC, TN, TP) of fine soil using multiple changes in geospatial parameters, trends in their mapping in future sedimentation areas and the drought-affected areas of South Korea, as well as the maximum burden of pollutants on the inhabitants of the Hwanghae Inland (located in southern Iraq), are also being investigated. The multimodal therapy is compared with the use of two and three biologics to achieve (Li et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022; Yuan et al.2020).

Air Quality Monitoring

With the development of industry, agriculture, and the increase of global population, the increasingly severe environmental pollution has caused environmental problems and threats to the physical and mental health of relevant personnel. How to use comprehensive, continuous, and efficient methods to evaluate and mitigate environmental pollution has become a hot research direction. This process has received increasing attention from professionals because it can evaluate the spatial and temporal changes of pollutants effectively and in a short time, thus helping to develop measures to control the spread of pollutants (Shen et al., 2020; Xiao et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2020).

Since air is an essential factor influencing human health and climate, air quality monitoring is an essential part of environmental pollution assessment. In the past few decades, remote sensing techniques have played an essential role in the field of air quality monitoring. The main methods of the air quality-related monitoring by remote sensing include the retrieval of columnar gas pollutants based on differential optical absorption spectroscopy (DOAS) theory and the retrieval of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and the concentration of atmospheric aerosol. There is, therefore, an increasing set of satellite and ground-based instruments that are able to link into these regimes, to enable rapid progress in air pollution observations at all temporal and spatial scales. However, there are still some challenging aspects in air quality-related monitoring by remote sensing-derived methods. The satellite-based technique cannot flexibly reach higher spatial resolution and temporal resolution at the same time, and the ground-based monitoring cannot obtain a larger scale resolved map. Furthermore, retrieval of the accurate concentration of the pollutants only based on the spectral information faces many errors caused by the reflection of ground light. The gradient of concentrations in the atmosphere between the instrument and the location of interest causes some influences on the retrieval of accurate concentration. It needs to use advanced algorithms to avoid the influence of

ground scaling effect. The comparison of retrieved and measured profile PM_{2.5} data of sum frequency of NDVI was made, and the result has presented that the differences were below 2%. Conversely, the PM_{2.5} retrieval accuracy is obviously decreased in foggy days. Clearly, further studies are required to optimize the algorithm for the reduction of system error in PM_{2.5} retrieval. Therefore, a combination of remote sensing monitoring technology and the actual measured data in situ has been proposed to reduce a large amount of errors in remote sensing monitoring results in recent years (Li et al., 2020; Sokhi et al., 2021; Shelestov et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020).

Challenges and Limitations of Remote Sensing in Environmental Pollution Assessment

One of the foremost challenges of remote sensing technology is the spatial resolution with which the sensors observe the earth's surface. The trade-off in terms of spatial and temporal resolution can limit the capability of the systems in detection, assessment, and gaining insights into environmental pollution, given its inherent complexity and rapid alterations. In the realm of air pollution characterization, low spatial resolution can thwart the process by limiting the sheer number of observations and confidence that can be achieved. Another constraint lies in the temporal resolution of remote sensing systems. The revisit interval of a satellite sensor, which is the length of time it takes for a sensor to return to the same location on Earth, can significantly hinder the tracking of pollutant variations if such changes occur within time gaps of less than the revisit interval. A joint limitation of both spatial and temporal resolution is the derivation of information on that microscale level for an in-depth understanding of the interactions between pollutants and the influencing factors at the site of the observed anomaly. More exceptions are listed in Table 2 (Li et al., 2020; Trinder & Liu, 2020; Cheng et al., 2022).

Moreover, the inherent challenges with collecting and analyzing remote sensing data and a lack of one-size-fits-all solution limit use in pollution mitigation. Airborne or satellite, passive or active, and multiple scanning mechanisms can provide an unwieldy array of programs that do not optimally complement a given pollutant distribution. While area emissions can have strong pollutant signals in remote sensing readings, odor emissions, punctual point source emissions, non-permanent pollution (accidental discharges), high natural background emissions or underground sources of volatile pollutants wouldn't always stand out in readings and identification. Different pixels of the same remote sensing product can have different unit areas delineated and data combinations are practically impossible. Source identification methodologies are also research areas and differ in complements of sources likely to be identified, areas that are downwind but not "improbably" contaminated, are based on receptor models requiring meteorological sensitive data, areas requiring post-satellite survey, and those usable for air quality management receptors. An evaluation of this "lack of understanding" is presented below in Section 6 (Yang et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2020; Avtar et al., 2020).

Spatial and Temporal Resolution Constraints

Spatial and temporal resolution constraints. In general, two factors determine the capabilities of remote sensing systems: spatial and spectral resolution. The spatial resolution of satellite sensors strongly constrains the representativeness of the data for any complex structure, such as a terrestrial system. Given the high variability of sources, the application of study is one of the major constraints for the use of air and space assets over land. Speaking about pollution, a direct consequence of degraded spatial representativeness is the problem of regional and local diffusion assessment and, consequently, of forecast. Because surface or remote sensing data have degraded spatial and/or time representativeness with respect to the characteristic of the exploration of gas pollutants, comparisons and assimilations of the

two different information sources are not directly possible or interpretable. For in situ data, one of the main limitations is also their reduced representativeness in space and time, and that they are conditional to specific sources (Wen et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2022; Dubovik et al., 2021; Nazeer et al., 2021).

There are "intermediate" solutions, even if partially effective, that have been attempted to mitigate the problem. Firstly, it is possible to increase the density of monitoring stations and the relative number of supervised systems, for the case of in situ measurement, representing an effective but expensive and complex strategy. In the case of MSG data, it is possible to use interpolated data from a limited number of fixed stations around the satellite overpass location to directly investigate modeling issues. Such artificial densification methods decrease the effects of spatial differences. More innovative solutions are needed and could resort to the increasing availability of very-high-spatial resolution satellite data, which are now at 0.4 m ground sampling distance, with revisit times from days to a few hours (e.g., DMC, RASAT, Pléiades, the WorldView series, high-resolution small-satellites constellations) (Chen et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2021; Borck & Schrauth, 2021).

Future Directions and Innovations in Remote Sensing for Environmental Pollution

Machine learning and artificial intelligence have the potential to considerably enhance the power of remote sensing in a number of ways. On one hand, they could have a huge impact on image pre-processing tasks (such as noise removal) and enable the retrieval of atmospheric parameters and the quantification of atmospheric compensation in a straightforward way. Additionally, advances in new machine learning algorithms, such as contrast gain control (CGC) or perspective change translation (PCT), and artificial intelligence (e.g., deep learning), enable efficient and straightforward object and feature recognition, named entity and landmark recognition, and intramodal and intermodal

mapping and image translation through classification. These could be applied in combination with remote sensing technology to solve a number of challenging problems. Importantly, the success of using deep learning architecture in dense matching tasks and opinion mining and analysis could considerably increase overall objectivity and efficiency, with the concomitant processing time reduction in these areas of environmental pollution and remote sensing. (Himeur et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022; Jia et al., 2021).

These innovative and cutting-edge technologies and approaches can be employed to address the limitations and challenges that have been discussed in the thematic section of this article. Moreover, they can be used to address limitations of existing novel approaches such as unmanned aerial systems. For instance, the application of virtual immersion and augmented reality could provide operational support to first response teams as well as solving intrinsic availability, high operational costs of stand-off remote sensing, and integrating and visualizing combined physical, chemical, biological, and atmospheric disaster data. It seems to hold great potential to increase training effectiveness in the application of emergency medical and environmental guidelines. This would eventually result in significant progress in near real-time pollution mapping, have real-life application for efficient responses, and increase emergency teams' situational awareness in relation to air, land, and marine pollution (Tan et al., 2022; Damaševičius et al., 2023; Sarker et al., 2020; Kucharczyk & Hugenholtz, 2021).

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence Applications

Recently, the growing interest in machine learning for processing large amounts of satellite and aerial data has also heavily influenced the field of environmental management. Machine learning techniques combined with geospatial data derived by remote sensing offer great opportunities to address environmental issues, such as oil spill detection, using multi-spectral information related to the absorption-emission properties of both the target pollutant and the

surrounding environment, classified using k-nearest neighbor algorithm, support vector machine, pixel-based image classification, convolutional neural network, and deep-learning network (Du et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2021; Costache et al., 2020; Shirmard et al., 2022).

Very innovative—and still not widely used—is the potential merge between remotely sensed data with artificial intelligence, computational techniques that can increase data's understanding when compared to mere automatic image analysis by machine learning. Indeed, machine learning opportunities mainly relate to data mining, data-driven analysis, and decision making. Artificial intelligence applications rather can simulate natural intelligence, reason, and learn with the environment, exhibit commonsense understanding, solve problems, possess social skills, and demonstrate creativity. Artificial intelligence used for pollution assessment and mitigation has wider applications but requires a very specific and deep know-how; therefore, it is still confined to the emerging literature. If the potentialities of artificial intelligence emerge in the environmental field, as also confirmed in expert surveys, e.g., deep learning has been coupled with Monte Carlo simulations for oil spill forecasting, the frame inside these technologies were used is not suitable for a conclusive and comprehensive review. To our knowledge, a narrative review outlining machine learning and artificial intelligence progress in individual model tools or applications is a topic yet to be thoroughly examined. (Zhang & Zhang, 2022; Yang et al., 2022; Fuentes-Peñailillo et al., 2024; Kamyab et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Remote sensing is gradually revolutionizing the field of environmental pollution assessment and mitigation because of its potential in different aspects of monitoring like geographical coverage, cost-effective, user-friendly higher resolution, sensitive for multi-pollutants, quick, and providing digital data. The importance of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in environmental monitoring programs has

recently been highlighted. This narrative article accounted for the role of remote sensing in mitigating and assessing numerous types of environmental pollution, like water pollution, soil pollution, air pollution, mining-inflicted pollution, oil disaster/industrial air pollution, radiological pollution, light pollution, and noise pollution. Moreover, this review outlined the existing apprehension on developing platforms through presentation of implications and reports. Over a decade, implicit advancements have been increasingly accrued, like good practices for data acquisition, data fusion/gamma synergy products, image-based sensors, key limitations, challenging aspects, and solution for ground-based monitoring. An overview of developments and advancements was done through a widespread appraisal of a number of floods concerning advancements indicating the potential implications.

In the aftermath, progress has been observed in both natural and synthetic/inflectional flow indices. On the whole, participation and collaborations from the broader scientific community are required for improved employability and, consequently, for validation and uptake. A necessary potential suggestion direction was emerging using this opportunity. This review has highlighted the benefits and scope of remote sensing in the ability to evaluate and mitigate environmental pollution for researchers and as a guide for developing countries.

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